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Year 45, Issue 3, April to June 2022

इंडियन इन्स्टिट्यूट ऑव्ह एज्युकेशन
जे. पी. नाईक पथ, कोथरुड, पुणे- ४११ ०३८

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Quarterly dedicated to the policy of 'Education through Social
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ह्या धोरणास वाहिलेले त्रैमासिक

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Educational Aspirations among Senior Secondary School Students of East Sikkim

Jayashree Prasad*

T J M S Raju**

Abstract:

The present study aims to find the level of educational aspirations among senior secondary school students of East Sikkim. The main objectives of this research is to study about Gender, Management, Stream and Class of Senior Secondary School Students of East Sikkim on Educational Aspirations. The data were collected from 100 Senior Secondary School Students of East Sikkim by using the tool Constructed and Standardized by Sharma V. P. & Anuradha Gupta (2015). The tool consists of 45 items constitute the total educational aspirations of the students. The data were analysed with the help of statistical analysis by using Mean, S.D and 't' ratios. The outcomes of the study were deliberated according to the substantial values obtained. Based on the significant values certain responses, findings and conclusion were drawn.

Key Words: Educational Aspirations, Senior Secondary School Students, Gender, Management, Stream.

Introduction:

Aspiration, basically, is an expression of a willingness to achieve and improve. Educational aspirations are educational goals set by students for themselves. Operationally, Educational Aspiration can be defined as a student's ability to identify, determine and set future goals while breathing in the present to achieve these goals. According to Sirin et al. (2004) "Aspirations have been defined as educational and vocational dreams that students have for the future." Since, the life of the student involves many desires, interests, successes, failures and the level of motivation and aspiration level, achievement, success and failure play an important role in students' lives and activities. Students must be aware of their abilities and have self-insight in various things. Although educational aspirations are important, educational expectations can provide a more specific and realistic assessment that serves as a "cognitive link" between the idealized aspirations and future educational

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attainment (Reynolds and Pemberton, 2001). Therefore, the aspiration as a goal-seeking behaviour is basic feature of the modern competitive world.

The term "educational aspiration level," used in this study refers an individual's desire to achieve a certain future state by him, and whether the intelligent activities in the classroom are affected by learning. According to this definition, the researcher assumes that some students reach a higher level of education and satisfy the desires of their parents and other important figures through academic and social integration into campus life. In the study of Sewell and Hauser (1980), it showed that men's educational aspirations are more influenced by ability, by high school grades and by the support and role models of other important figures.

Therefore, everyone has ambitions. At all stages of life, people are trying to improve themselves. The aspirations of students will influence their behaviour. The term educational aspiration or vocational choice is based on an understanding of characteristics. The level of aspirations of an individual is an important motivating factor. It is a frame of reference that involves self-esteem or the alternative experience of failure or success.

Rashmi Garg, Carol Kauppi, John Lewko & Diana Urajnik (2002) conducted a study on A Structural Model of Educational Aspirations. Educational aspirations was the main outcome variable. Results indicated that the personal factor had a strong direct influence on educational aspirations. The findings emphasize the importance of efforts to enhance the educational aspirations of adolescents through targeted change of modifiable environmental and personal factors.

Rajesh & Chandrasekaran (2014) conducted a study on Educational Aspirations of High School Students. There is no significant difference in high school students' Educational Aspirations with respect to their Type of School Management, Educational Qualification of Father, Educational Qualification of Mother, Occupation of Father and Family Income.

Rani & Setia (2016) conducted a study on Educational Aspiration of +2 Students in Relation to Family Environment. It is inferred from the results that there is significant difference in educational aspiration level of +2 boy and girl students. So, "There exists no significant difference in the educational aspiration of +2 boy and girl students." Stands accepted", cannot be rejected. Hence the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Raja (2016) conducted a study on A Study on Level of Educational Aspiration of High School Students. In the study result shows that 0% of students show low level of educational aspirations and 30% of students show average level of educational aspirations and remaining 70% of students shows high level of educational aspirations.

Chawla (2018) Examined a study on A Study of Educational Aspirations of Secondary School Students in relation to their Achievement Scores. It was found that there exists no significant difference in educational aspirations of secondary school students with respect to type of school. There exists no significant difference in educational aspirations of secondary school students with respect to gender.

Negel & Pramanik (2019) Conducted a study on Level of Aspiration and its Relation to Academic Performance of Higher Secondary School Students. Ho1: There is no significant difference between level of aspiration and academic performance of higher secondary school students. Ho2: There is no significant difference between level of aspiration and academic performance of higher secondary rural and urban school students. Ho3: There is no significant difference between level of aspiration and academic performance of higher secondary male and female school students. So that the study also realizes the necessity to investigate any success of learners is significantly influenced by aspiration which factors determine them in order to have a better understanding of the students and help them to guide in the right direction without losing the most precious resource.

Rationale of the Study:

In this present context, investigator wants to study Educational Aspirations of Senior Secondary school Students of East Sikkim. In the context of Sikkim hardly any research has been conducted on Educational Aspirations of Senior Secondary school Students of East Sikkim. In Sikkim young individual's future in today's technological society depends entirely on his education. Therefore, in order to attain and achieve success in life one should have realistic educational aspiration. Thus, educational aspirations of senior secondary school students play an important role in preparing the individuals for a better future. The aspirations and expectations of students have changed with time. The principal, teachers and indirectly the management has to manage their aspirations and expectations. It is important to understand the desires and expectations of a student so that changes are brought and there is a smooth functioning of the school. Hence, the researcher has taken an attempt to measure the educational aspirations level among senior secondary school students of east Sikkim. The idea to conducting this study is to find out the key to identify, what level of student's ability to set goals for the future and this study has given an attempt to find out the root cause as well as the solution to provide them with proper guidance on Educational Aspirations of Senior Secondary school Students of East Sikkim.

When the researcher is reviewing a study on educational aspirations conducted on Sikkim State it has been understood that there is no study so

far on educational aspirations. Based on these lines the researcher has the topic to understand the educational aspirations among senior secondary school students. This study is significant as it will provide some insight on the level of educational aspiration among senior secondary school students of Sikkim.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the educational aspirations of senior secondary students of East Sikkim with regard to their gender.
2. To study the educational aspirations of senior secondary students of East Sikkim with regard to their management.
3. To study the educational aspirations of senior secondary students of East Sikkim with regard to their stream.
4. To study the educational aspirations of senior secondary students of East Sikkim with regard to their class.

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses have been set up for the study.

- HO1: There is no significant difference between senior secondary school boys and girls of East Sikkim with regard to their gender.
- HO2: There is no significant difference between senior secondary school boys and girls of East Sikkim with regard to their management.
- HO3: There is no significant difference between senior secondary school boys and girls of East Sikkim with regard to their stream.
- HO4: There is no significant difference between senior secondary school boys and girls of East Sikkim with regard to their class.

Delimitations of the Study:

The following are the delimitations of the study:

1. The study is delimited to four objectives namely gender, management, stream and class only.
2. The study is delimited to the sample size of 100 only.
3. The study is delimited to the senior secondary school students only.

Operational definition of the terms study:

Educational Aspirations: Educational Aspirations according to present study refers as an expression of the desire to achieve and improve. It is a level of motivation that overcomes task complexity with perpetual efforts and pushes one to work towards these goals.

Senior Secondary School Students: It connotes the students studying in class XI & XII of East district of Sikkim. Simply we can say ‘adolescent’ student.

The Design:

The descriptive survey method has used in the current research. The data was collected by the questionnaire in survey method. It is considered to be an appropriate method, because the evidence concerning the existing situation would be secured and norms would be identified to compare the present positions and also for the further plan of actions.

The Sample:

A sample of 100 senior secondary school students has been selected from the East Sikkim. Out of 100 students, 50 boys and 50 girls has been selected from east district of Sikkim. Stratified random sampling technique has been used in the present study.

Tool used in the Present Study:

Scale of level of Educational Aspiration Inventory constructed and standardized by Dr. V.P. Sharma and Anuradha Gupta (2015) on Senior Secondary school student. This tool consists of 45 items and each item consists of two options i. e. A & B. For the correct response one mark should be awarded and the range of this scoring is 0 to 45 marks. All items are positive and highest scores considered as highest level of Educational Aspirations.

Statistics used:

Mean, SD and t-Test were used to calculate the significant values. Means denotes the averages of the total EA scores, SD shows the deviations of the scores from the mean and the t-Values provides the significant difference between the two groups.

Table 1

The comparison between Gender on Educational Aspirations of Senior Secondary School Students of East Sikkim are given below. (Boys-50, Girls-50, N=100)

S. No.	Variable	Gender	Means	SD	t-Values
1.	Educational Aspirations	Boys 50	27.00	6.26	0.433@
		Girls 50	27.50	5.23	
@Not Significant.					

From the above table the 't' value 0.433 is not significant at 0.01 level and 0.05 level. Hence, H1 accepted. So, we conclude that there is no significant difference between level of aspiration among senior secondary boys and girl school students. However, Analysis of data for H1, there is no significant difference between level of educational aspiration among senior secondary boys and girl school students.

Table 2

The comparison between Management on Educational Aspirations of Senior Secondary School Students of East Sikkim are given below. (Government-60, Private-40, N=100)

S.No.	Variable	Management	Means	SD	t-Values
1.	Educational Aspirations	Government	27.1333	4.49281	0.23@
		Private	27.4250	7.30608	
@ Not Significant.					

From the above table the 't' value 0.23 is not significant at 0.01 level and 0.05 level. Hence, H2 accepted. So, we conclude that there is no significant difference between level of aspiration among senior secondary government and private school students. However, Analysis of data for H2, there is no significant difference between level of educational aspiration among senior secondary government and private school students.

Table 3

The comparison between stream on Educational Aspirations of Senior Secondary School Students of East Sikkim are given below. (Arts-40, Science-60, N=100)

S. No.	Variable	Stream	Means	SD	t-Values
1.	Educational Aspirations	Arts	27.0250	4.12303	0.35@
		Science	27.4000	6.64907	
@ Not Significant.					

From the above table the 't' value 0.433 is not significant at 0.01 level and 0.05 level. Hence, H3 accepted. So, we conclude that there is no significant difference between level of aspiration among senior secondary arts and science school students. However, Analysis of data for H3, there is no significant difference between level of educational aspiration among senior secondary arts and science school students.

Table 4

The comparison between Class on Educational Aspirations of Senior Secondary School Students of East Sikkim are given below. (XI-40, XII-60, N=100)

S.No.	Variable	Class	Means	SD	t-Values
1.	Educational Aspirations	XI	27.0250	4.12303	0.35@
		XII	27.4000	6.64907	
@ Not Significant.					

From the above table the 't' value 0.35 is not significant at 0.01 level and 0.05 level. Hence, H₄ accepted. So, we conclude that there is no significant difference between level of aspiration among senior secondary class XI and class XII school students. However, Analysis of data for H₄, there is no significant difference between level of educational aspiration among senior secondary class XI and class XII school students.

Major Findings:

After analysis of tabulated data the investigator found out the following findings.

1. There is no significant difference between senior secondary school boys and girls on their educational aspirations.
2. There is no significant difference between senior secondary school government and private on their educational aspirations.
3. There is no significant difference between senior secondary school arts and science on their educational aspirations.
4. There is no significant difference between senior secondary school XI and XII on their educational aspirations.

Conclusion:

1. Both boys and girls are having same level of educational aspirations.
2. Both government and private boys and girls are having same level of educational aspirations.
3. Both arts and science boys and girls are having same level of educational aspirations.
4. Both XI and XII boys and girls are having same level of educational aspirations.

References:

1. Beal, Sarah, J.; Crockett, & Lisa., J. (2010). Adolescents occupational and educational aspirations and expectations: Links to high school activities and adult educational attainment. *Developmental Psychology*, 46(1), 258-265.
2. Chawla, M (2018). A Study of Educational Aspirations of Secondary School Students in relation to their Achievement Scores. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*. 8 (4).
3. Garg, R., Kauppi, C., Lewko, J., & Urajnik., D. (2002). A Structural Model of Educational Aspirations. *Journal of Career Development* volume, 29, 87–108.
4. Negel, S., & Pramanik, K. C. (2019). Level of Aspiration and Its Relation to Academic Performance of Higher Secondary School Students. *International journal of basic and applied research*, 9 (6), 2249-3352.
5. Raja, S. (2016). A Study on Level of Educational Aspiration of High School Students. *International Journal of Science and Research*. 1 (3), 2319-7064.
6. Rajesh, V. R. & Chandrasekaran, V. (2014). Educational Aspirations of High School Students. *Indian Journal of Applied Research*. 4 (12), 2249-555X.
7. Rani. A & Setia, V (2016) Educational Aspiration of +2 Students in Relation to Family Environment. *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, 6 (12), 2249-555X.
8. Reynolds, J.R., & Pemberton, J. (2001). Rising college expectations among youth in the United States: A comparison of the 1979 and 1997 NLSY. *The Journal of Human Resources*, 36(4), 703–26.
9. Sewell, W. & Hauser, R. (1980). The Wisconsin longitudinal study of social and psychological factors in aspirations and achievements. In A. C. Kerckhoff,(Ed), *Research in Sociology of Education and Socialization*. (59-99). Greenwich: JAI Press.
10. Sharma, V. P., & Gupta, A. (2015). *Manual for Educational Aspiration Scale*, National Psychological Corporation,4/230,Kacheri Ghat, Agra, India.
11. Sirin, S.R., Diemer, M.A., Jackson, L.R., & Howell, A. (2004). Future aspirations of urban adolescents. A person-in-context model. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 17, 437-459.

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